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World Inventory of Beetles of the Subfamily *Epilachninae* Mulsant, 1846 (Coleoptera: *Coccinellidae*). Check List from 1758 to 2003

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents list of beetles of the Subfamily *Epilachninae* Mulsant, 1846 (Family *Coccinellidae* Latreille, 1807) and their occurrence. The paper includes: 4 tribes, 23 genera and 1051 species of beetles belonging to the subfamily *Epilachninae*.

Keywords: Coleoptera, *Coccinellidae*, *Epilachninae*, *Epilachnini*, *Cynegetini*, *Epivertini*, *Eremochilini*

Tribes

<i>Epilachnini</i>2
<i>Cynegetini</i>64
<i>Epivertini</i>70
<i>Eremochilini</i>70

Kingdom: *Animalia*

Phylum: *Arthropoda*

Class: *Hexapoda*

Order: *Coleoptera*

Family *Coccinellidae* Latreille, 1807

Subfamily *Epilachninae* Mulsant, 1846

Tribe *Epilachnini* Mulsant, 1846

Genus *Adira* Gordon et Almeida, 1986

Adira clarkii (Crotch, 1874)

Distribution: Brazil

Adira gossypiata (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Bolivia

Adira gossypioides (Gordon, 1975)

Distribution: Panama, Colombia

Adira inexculpta (Gordon, 1975)

Distribution: Bolivia

Adira nucula (Weise, 1902)

Distribution: Peru

Adira obscurocincta (Klug, 1829)

Distribution: Brazil, Bolivia, Uruguay, Paraguay, Argentina

Adira richteri (Gordon, 1975)

Distribution: Colombia

Adira subcincta (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Colombia

Adira tomentosa (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Brazil, French Guiana

Genus *Afidenta* Dieke, 1947

Afidenta alia (Mader, 1955)

Distribution: Kenya, Tanzania, Rwanda, Zaire

Afidenta arisana Li in Li et Cook, 1961

Distribution: Taiwan

Afidenta capicola (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Republic of South Africa

Afidenta dahlbomi (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Republic of South Africa, Mozambique

Afidenta dolosa (Weise, 1897)

Distribution: Tanzania, Zaire

Afidenta ephippiata (Weise, 1898)

Distribution: Tanzania, Zaire

Afidenta exagitata Chazeau, 1976

Distribution: Madagascar

Afidenta flavomarginata (Korschefsky, 1947)

Distribution: Tanzania

Afidenta godarti (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Ethiopia, Butrundi, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, Republic of South Africa, Angola

Afidenta gyllenhalli (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Togo, Cameroon, Zaire, Kenya, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, Republic of South Africa

Afidenta hafa Chazeau, 1976

Distribution: Madagascar

Afidenta inetrmedia (Weise, 1926)

Distribution: Sudan, Ethiopia, Kenya, Uganda, Zaire

Afidenta inversa (Sicard, 1912)

Distribution: Tanzania, Uganda, Zaire

Afidenta janczyki Fursch, 1986

Distribution: Rwanda

Afidenta kenyana Fursch, 1986

Distribution: Kenya, Tanzania

Afidenta kwaiensis (Weise, 1897)

Distribution: Tanzania, Zaire, Rwanda, Uganda

Afidenta maderi (Korschefsky, 1947)

Distribution: Tanzania

Afidenta mahalana Chazeau, 1976

Distribution: Madagascar

Afidenta malawiensis Fursch, 1996

Distribution: Malawi

Afidenta maotina Chazeau, 1976

Distribution: Madagascar

Afidenta marginata (Korschefsky, 1934)

Distribution: Zambia, Mozambique

Afidenta mediofasciata (Sicard, 1930)

Distribution: Zaire, Congo, Cameroon, Guinea, Sierra Leone

Afidenta meruensis (Weise, 1909)

Distribution: Zaire, Kenya, Tanzania, Rwanda, Mozambique

Afidenta misera (Weise, 1901)

Distribution: India, Sri Lanka, Nepal, China, Taiwan, Vietnam, Philippines, Indonesia (Timor I.)

Afidenta muehlei Fursch, 1997

Distribution: Rwanda

Afidenta pauliani Chazeau, 1976

Distribution: Madagascar

Afidenta pellex (Weise, 1899)

Distribution: Tanzania

Afidenta razafimandimbyi Chazeau, 1976

Distribution: Madagascar

Afidenta rhizobioides (Weise, 1910)

Distribution: Madagascar

Afidenta rhombophora (Mader, 1955)

Distribution: Tanzania, Rwanda

Afidenta rhombophoroides (Fursch, 1960)

Distribution: Tanzania

Afidenta saegeri Fursch, 1986

Distribution: Zaire, Tanzania, Republic of Central Africa

Afidenta scitula (Weise, 1898)

Distribution: Cameroon, Zaire

Afidenta siamensis (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: China, Thailand

Afidenta straelini (Mader, 1957)

Distribution: Zaire

Afidenta tripartita (Sicard, 1912)

Distribution: Zaire, Uganda

Afidenta tsynadika Chazeau, 1976

Distribution: Madagascar

Afidenta vazimba Chazeau, 1976

Distribution: Madagascar

Afidenta vitabeata Chazeau, 1975

Distribution: Madagascar

Afidenta zernyi (Korschefsky, 1947)

Distribution: Tanzania

Genus ***Afidentula*** Kapur, 1958

Afidentula aruensis (Crotch, 1874)

Distribution: Aru Is., New Guinea

Afidentula bisquadrupunctata (Gyllenhal in Schonherr, 1808)

Distribution: China, Vietnam, India, Nepal, Sri Lanka

Afidentula bivakana Bielawski, 1965

Distribution: New Guinea

Afidentula cucphuongensis Hoang, 1977

Distribution: Vietnam

Afidentula decimaculata Cao et Wang in Wang et Cao, 1992

Distribution: China (Yunnan)

Afidentula erberi Fursch, 1984

Distribution: Pakistan

Afidentula herbigrada (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: India, Sri Lanka

Afidentula himalayana Kapur, 1963

Distribution: India (Sikkim, Darjeeling, Uttar Pradesh)

Afidentula kapuri Bielawski, 1965

Distribution: New Guinea

Afidentula manderstjerna (Mulsant, 1853)

Distribution: China, Vietnam, India, Nepal

Afidentula minima (Gorham, 1894)

Distribution: India

Afidentula nasti Bielawski, 1963

Distribution: New Guinea

Afidentula quindecimguttata (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: China

Afidentula stephensi (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: India, Nepal

Afidentula tenmana Bielawski, 1965

Distribution: New Guinea

Afidentula thanhsonensis Hoang, 1977

Distribution: Vietnam

Afidentula watalai Jadwiszczak, 1986

Distribution: New Guinea

Afidentula wiebesi Bielawski, 1965

Distribution: New Guinea

Genus *Afissula* Kapur, 1958

Afissula antennata Bielawski, 1967

Distribution: Burma

Afissula burmana (Bielawski, 1967)

Distribution: Burma

Afissula chapaensis Hoang, 1977

Distribution: Vietnam

Afissula expansa (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: China

Afissula hydrangeae Pang et Mao, 1979

Distribution: China

Afissula hyla Bielawski, 1967

Distribution: Burma

Afissula kambaitana (Bielawski, 1967)

Distribution: Burma, China, Nepal

Afissula merkli Jadwiszczak, 1989

Distribution: India (Darjeeling)

Afissula mysticoides (Sicard, 1913)

Distribution: India, Nepal, China

Afissula nonggangensis Zeng et Yang, 1996

Distribution: China

Afissula orinthorrhyncha Zeng et Yang, 1996

Distribution: China

Afissula parvula (Crotch, 1874)

Distribution: India, Nepal

Afissula puncta Bielawski, 1967

Distribution: Burma

Afissula rana Kapur, 1958

Distribution: Nepal, China

Afissula sadonensis (Bielawski, 1967)

Distribution: Burma

Afissula sanscrita (Crotch, 1874)

Distribution: China (Tibet), India (Sikkim)

Afissula spatulata Cao et Xiao, 1984

Distribution: China

Afissula uniformis Pang et Mao, 1979

Distribution: China

Afissula yunnanica Cao et Wang, 1992
Distribution: China (Yunnan)

Genus *Chnootriba* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Chnootriba curriei Casey, 1899
Distribution: Liberia, Sierra Leone, Ivory Coast

Chnootriba erectepubescens Mader, 1941
Distribution: Congo, Cameroon

Chnootriba fortepunctata Mader, 1957
Distribution: Zaire

Chnootriba hippodamoides Weise, 1885
Distribution: Congo, Zaire

Chnootriba lata Sicard, 1912
Distribution: Zaire, Uganda

Chnootriba maderi Fursch, 1960
Distribution: Zaire, Tanzania

Chnootriba neglecta Mader, 1941
Distribution: Zaire, Rwanda, Uganda, Kenya, Tanzania

Chnootriba opaca Fursch, 1960
Distribution: Tanzania

Chnootriba pajori Fursch, 1996
Distribution: Republic of South Africa

Chnootriba similis (Thunberg, 1781)
Distribution: Liberia, Sierra Leone, Cameroon, Ivory Coast, Congo, Zaire, Uganda, Rwanda, Ethiopia, Kenya, Republic of South Africa

Genus *Epilachna* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Epilachna abrupta Gorham, 1897
Distribution: Costa Rica, Panama

Epilachna aculata Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna acuta (Weise, 1889)

Distribution: China, Taiwan

Epilachna admirabilis Crotch 1874

Distribution: Japan, China, Taiwan, Vietnam

Epilachna adnexa (Mader, 1958)

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna adscita (Mader, 1930)

Distribution: China

Epilachna advena (Mader, 1954)

Distribution: Zaire, Kenya, Tanzania

Epilachna aemula (Weise, 1899)

Distribution: Rwanda, Uganda, Tanzania

Epilachna aemuloides Fursch, 1987

Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna aenigma (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire, Rwanda

Epilachna aequatorialis Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna aereipennis (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna aestimabilis (Mader, 1955)

Distribution: Zaire, Rwanda

Epilachna aggregata Fursch, 1985

Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna agnata (Mader, 1957)

Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna albovittata (Weise, 1906)

Distribution: Argentina

Epilachna alluaudi (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna alternans Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Indonesia (Java)

Epilachna ambigua (Mader, 1958)

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna ambrensis (Sicar, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna amharae Fursch, 1963

Distribution: Ethiopia

Epilachna amorpha Arrow, 1909

Distribution: Uganda

Epilachna ampliata Pang et Mao, 1979

Distribution: China

Epilachna amplipunctata Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Nova Grenada

Epilachna andrewesi Gorham, 1903

Distribution: India

Epilachna angusta Li in Li et Cook, 1961

Distribution: China, Taiwan

Epilachna angustata Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Venezuela

Epilachna anhweiana (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: China

Epilachna animula Fursch, 1987

Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna annamensis (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna annexa Weise, 1895

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna anthodea Zeng et Yang, 1996

Distribution: China

Epilachna anthracina (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna apiceoculata Fursch, 1997

Distribution: Rwanda

Epilachna approximata Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna argiola Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna atrosinuata (Fursch, 1960)

Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna atypica (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: India, Indonesia (Flores I.)

Epilachna aubei Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Mexico

Epilachna aulisoides (Weise, 1919)

Distribution: Zaire, Rwanda, Ethiopia

Epilachna aurea Fursch, 1987

Distribution: Ruwenzori Mts. (Uganda/Zaire)

Epilachna aureola Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru, Ecuador

Epilachna aureopilosa Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna auricoma (Sicard, 1912)

Distribution: Zimbabwe

Epilachna austrina Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Brazil, Uruguay

Epilachna axillaris Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Venezuela

Epilachna azurea (Castelnau, 1840)

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna basalis (Weise, 1900)

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna bengalica (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: India (Sikkim, North Bengal), Nepal, Bhutan

Epilachna bennigseni (Weise, 1899)

Distribution: Tanzania, Kenya, Ethiopia

Epilachna benschi (Sicard, 1912)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna berthae (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna besucheti Canepari, 1986

Distribution: India (Darjeeling)

Epilachna bhutanensis Bielawski, 1979

Distribution: Bhutan

Epilachna bicirculifera (Mader, 1955)

Distribution: Zaire, Rwanda, Tanzania

Epilachna bicrescens (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: China

Epilachna bifibra Li in Li et Cook, 1961

Distribution: Taiwan

Epilachna bifibulata Weise, 1895

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna bimaculicollis Sicard, 1922

Distribution: Republic of South Africa

Epilachna bisbivittata Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna bisdecempunctata (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire Rwanda

Epilachna bisdecemsignata (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire, Uganda, Tanzania

Epilachna bisellata (Sicard, 1912)

Distribution: Kenya

Epilachna bisoetonotata (Mader, 1957)

Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna bisquinquenotata (Mader, 1957)

Distribution: Central Africa (Kivu)

Epilachna bisseptemmaculata (Mader, 1955)

Distribution: Zaire, Kenya

Epilachna bissexguttata Weise, 1895

Distribution: Guinea, Liberia, Ivory Coast, Ghana, Cameroon, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Republic of South Africa, Zaire, Uganda, Rwanda

Epilachna bistriguttata Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna bistrisignata (Mader, 1950)

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna bistrispilota Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna bituberculata Waterhouse, 1879

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna bizonata Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna blaesa (Weise, 1905)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna blandula Fursch, 1963

Distribution: Rwanda

Epilachna bolivicola (Mader, 1950)

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna bomparti Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Senegal, Togo, Ivory Coast, Sierra Leone

Epilachna bonplandi Dejean, 1837

Distribution: Peru, Colombia

Epilachna boops Fursch, 1963

Distribution: Rwanda, Kenya, Tanzania

Epilachna boraustralis Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Venezuela, Colombia, Ecuador

Epilachna borealis (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution: North America

Epilachna boreli (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna bourcierii Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna bouvieri (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna boymi Jadwiszczak 2003

Distribution: China

Epilachna brachyloba Zeng et Yang, 1996

Distribution: China

Epilachna brivioi (Bielawski et Fursch, 1960)

Distribution: Burma

Epilachna buckleyi Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna cacica (Guerin-Meneville, 1944)

Distribution: Venezuela, Colombia, Ecuador, Peru, Bolivia, Brazil, Paraguay, Argentina

Epilachna calisto (Weise, 1899)

Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna callangae Gordon, 1900

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna calligrapta Gorham, 1897

Distribution: Panama

Epilachna canina (Fabricius, 1781)

Distribution: Mozambique, South Africa

Epilachna carapacola Fursch, 1997

Distribution: Rwanda

Epilachna caucaensis Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna championi Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Guatemala

Epilachna chapini (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Philippines

Epilachna chayuensis Pang et Mao, 1977

Distribution: China

Epilachna chelys Jadwiszczak, 2003

Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna cherrapunjiensis (Kapur, 1963)

Distribution: India

Epilachna chigata Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna chinensis (Weise, 1912)

Distribution: Japan, Korea, China, Taiwan, Vietnam

Epilachna chingjing Yu et Wang, 1999

Distribution: Taiwan

Epilachna ciliata Gordon, 1986

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna cinctipennis Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Venezuela

Epilachna cinerea Fursch, 1963

Distribution: Congo

Epilachna circulifera (Mader, 1955)

Distribution: Tanzania, Rwanda, Zaire

Epilachna circumcincta Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Brazil

Epilachna circumdata Hoang, 1978

Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna circummaculata Pang et Mao, 1977

Distribution: China (Tibet)

Epilachna clandestina Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Brazil

Epilachna clementicola Cao et Xiao, 1984

Distribution: China

Epilachna coccinelloides (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Brunei

Epilachna colombiana Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna colorata Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Senegal, Guinea, Togo, Cameroon, Gabon, Equatorial Guinea (Fernando Poo Is.), Zaire, Rwanda, Uganda

Epilachna compilata Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Indonesia (Java, Sumatra)

Epilachna completa (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: China

Epilachna complicata (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: China

Epilachna concolor Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Brazil

Epilachna concuongensis Hoang, 1978

Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna confixa Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna confusa Li in Li et Cook, 1961

Distribution: China, Taiwan

Epilachna congener Gorham, 1895

Distribution: Burma, India (Sikkim, West Bengal, Darjeeling)

Epilachna confifera Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Argentina, Bolivia

Epilachna conjuncta Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna conradti Weise, 1898

Distribution: Cameroon

Epilachna consignata (Weise, 1909)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna consimilis Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna conspergata Fursch, 1997

Distribution: Rwanda

Epilachna cosnputa Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: unknown

Epilachna consularis Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna convergens Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Ecuador, Peru

Epilachna convexa (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: China

Epilachna convextata Singh et Singh, 1990

Distribution: India

Epilachna coquereli (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna cordula (Weise, 1898)

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna cormosana Gestro, 1895

Distribution: Somalia

Epilachna corniventris Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna crassimala Li in Li et Cook, 1961

Distribution: China, Taiwan

Epilachna crecentomaculata Singh et Singh, 1990

Distribution: India

Epilachna cribrata Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Angola

Epilachna cruciata Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Venezuela

Epilachna counaensis Pang et Mao, 1977

Distribution: China

Epilachna cuscoi Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna cushmani Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna darlingtoni Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna dawkinsi Li, 1993

Distribution: Australia

Epilachna decellei Fursch, 1987

Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna decemguttata (Weise, 1923)

Distribution: Taiwan

Epilachna decemmaculata Redtenbacher in Kollar et Redtenbacher, 1844

Distribution: India (Kashmir), Burma, China (Tibet), Sri Lanka

Epilachna decipiens Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Indonesia (Java)

Epilachna delessertii (Guerin-Meneville, 1840)

Distribution: India, Sri Lanka

Epilachna deleta Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Sierra Leone, Zaire, Burundi, Tanzania, Kenya, Ethiopia

Epilachna deltoides Weise, 1895

Distribution: Cameroon, Angola, Republic of Central Africa, Zaire

Epilachna densevestita (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna deuterea Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Venezuela

Epilachna deyrollii Crotch, 1874

Distribution: India (Darjeeling, Sikkim), Burma

Epilachna difficilis Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Guatemala, Mexico

Epilachna discincta Weise, 1890

Distribution: Mexico, Guatemala, Belize, Honduras

Epilachna discoidea Erichson, 1847

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna discolor Erichson, 1847

Distribution: Peru, Bolivia

Epilachna discrepens (Weise, 1901)

Distribution: Tanzania, South Africa

Epilachna distincta (Thunberg, 1781)

Distribution: Republic of South Africa

Epilachna diversipes (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna dives Erichson, 1847

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna divisa (Weise, 1900)

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna divisoides (Gordon, 1975)

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna dobzhanskyi (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: China

Epilachna dohrni Weise, 1888

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna donckieri (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna donghoiensis Hoang, 1978

Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna dorotae Bielawski, 1979

Distribution: Bhutan

Epilachna dorsigera Erichson, 1847

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna dregei Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Sudan, South Africa

Epilachna dubia Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna dufourii Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Guinea, Central Africa, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, Mozambique

Epilachna dumerili Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Sri Lanka, Nepal, Burma, China, Vietnam

Epilachna duodecimpustulosa Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: South Africa

Epilachna duvivieriorum (Weise, 1898) emend.

Distribution: Zimbabwe

Epilachna eckloni Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: South Africa

Epilachna ecuadorica Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna ellisi Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna elongatula Jadwiszczak, 2003

Distribution: East Africa

Epilachna elvina Mulsant, 1853

Distribution: India, Nepal

Epilachna emerita Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna endomycina Gorham, 1903

Distribution: India

Epilachna erichsoni Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Panama

Epilachna erinacea (Sicard, 1925)

Distribution: South India

Epilachna erythrotricha Hoang, 1978

Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna esemephata Gordon, 1986

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna eusema (Weise, 1904)

Distribution: Argentina, Bolivia, Peru

Epilachna excisa Weise, 1895

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna eximia Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna exornata Bielawski, 1965
Distribution: China (Yunnan)

Epilachna extrema Crotch, 1874
Distribution: Colombia, Ecuador

Epilachna fallax (Weise, 1908)
Distribution: Indonesia (Borneo)

Epilachna fansipana Hoang, 1978
Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna fasciata (Sicard, 1912)
Distribution: Kenia, Uganda

Epilachna fascifera (Mader, 1941)
Distribution: Zaire, Rwanda

Epilachna fasciolata Crotch, 1874
Distribution: India

Epilachna fausta Erichson, 1874
Distribution: Peru

Epilachna fenchinica Pang, 1993
Distribution: Taiwan

Epilachna fenestrata Erichson, 1847
Distribution: Peru, Bolivia

Epilachna fenestroides Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Peru

Epilachna flavicollis Thunberg, 1781
Distribution: India, Sri Lanka, China, Taiwan, Thailand, Burma, Vietnam, Philippines, Indonesia (Sumatra, Java, Borneo, Celebes)

Epilachna flavimarginalis Hoang, 1978
Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna flavofaciata (Castelnau, 1840)
Distribution: Venezuela, Colombia, Ecuador, Peru

Epilachna flavopustulata Kolbe, 1897
Distribution: Ruwenzori, Uganda

Epilachna folifera Pang et Mao, 1979
Distribution: China

Epilachna formosana (Weise, 1923)
Distribution: Taiwan

Epilachna forsteri (Mader, 1958)
Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna freudei (Mader, 1958)
Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna freyana Bielawski, 1965
Distribution: China

Epilachna fryii Crotch, 1874
Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna fugongensis Cao et Xiao, 1984
Distribution: China

Epilachna fulvohirta Weise, 1895
Distribution: Gabon, Cameroon

Epilachna furcata Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna furtiva Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Peru

Epilachna fuscopilosa (Weise, 1902)
Distribution: Peru

Epilachna galerucinoides Korschefsky, 1934
Distribution: China, Vietnam, Indonesia (Flores, Sumba), Australia

Epilachna gallaensis Fursch, 1987
Distribution: Ethiopia

Epilachna gedeensis (Dieke, 1947)
Distribution: China, Indonesia (Java)

Epilachna gelensis Fursch, 1987
Distribution: Sudan

Epilachna gentilis (Weise, 1901)
Distribution: Kenya, Tanzania (including Zanzibar)

Epilachna geoffroyi Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna geometrica (Weise, 1900)

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna gibbera Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Nepal, India (Sikkim)

Epilachna gibbosa Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Cameroon, Equatorial Guinea (Fernando Poo Is.), Angola, Zaire, Kenya, Tanzania

Epilachna gloiera Xiao in Xiao et Li, 1992

Distribution: China (Sichuan)

Epilachna glochinosa Pang et Mao, 1979

Distribution: China

Epilachna glochisifoliata Pang et Mao, 1979

Distribution: China

Epilachna gnoma Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna godmani Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Guatemala

Epilachna goeteli Jadwischczak, 2003

Distribution: Cameroon, Equatorial Guinea

Epilachna gokteika (Kapur, 1963)

Distribution: Burma, Vietnam

Epilachna gordonii Jadwischczak, 2003

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna gorhami Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Costa Rica, Guatemala

Epilachna gorkhana Miyatake, 1985

Distribution: Nepal

Epilachna grandidieri (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna graphiptera (Sicard, 1930)

Distribution: Congo

Epilachna graueri (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire, Tanzania

Epilachna grayi Mulsant 1850

Distribution: India (Assam, North Bengal, Uttar Pradesh), Nepal, China, Indonesia (Java, Sumatra)

Epilachna gressitti Li in Li et Cook, 1961

Distribution: Taiwan

Epilachna gyldenstolpei (Weise, 1924)

Distribution: Zaire, Rwanda, Uganda

Epilachna haefligeri (Weise, 1906)

Distribution: Cameroon

Epilachna harmala (Weise, 1898)

Distribution: Cameroon, Togo

Epilachna harringtoni Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna hatinhensis Hoang, 1978

Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna hedwiga Weise, 1897

Distribution: Tanzania, Kenya

Epilachna hektea Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna hendecaspilota (Mader, 1927)

Distribution: India Sri Lanka, Nepal, Burma, Thailand, Vietnam, China, Taiwan, Philippines

Epilachna hignstoni (Kapur, 1963)

Distribution: North India, Nepal, China (Tibet)

Epilachna holmgreni (Weise, 1926)

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna honesta (Weise, 1900)

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna hopeiana Miyatake, 1985
Distribution: Nepal

Epilachna horioni (Fursch, 1960)
Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna hova (Weise, 1905)
Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna hovana Sicard, 1907
Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna humbloti (Sicard, 1907)
Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna hybridula Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Ecuador, Bolivia

Epilachna ignobilis (Weise, 1902)
Distribution: Peru

Epilachna imitata (Weise, 1899)
Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna impicticollis Sicard, 1910
Distribution: India

Epilachna incaorum Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Peru

Epilachna incauta Mulsant, 1850
Distribution: Taiwan, Burma, Indonesia (Java, Sumatra)

Epilachna indosinensis (Dieke, 1947)
Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna inedita (Mader, 1955)
Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna inexpectata (Sicard, 1907)
Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna infirma Mulsant, 1850
Distribution: Republic of South Africa

Epilachna innuba (Olivier, 1791)
Distribution: Orient

Epilachna inserta (Weise, 1900)

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna insignis Gorham, 1892

Distribution: China

Epilachna intermixta (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: India

Epilachna iocosa (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire, Tanzania, Rwanda

Epilachna jarugui Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna jianchuanensis Cao et Xiao, 1984

Distribution: China

Epilachna jole (Weise, 1899)

Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna julii (Ricard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna juvenca Weise, 1897

Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna kaestneri Fursch, 1963

Distribution: Zaire, Uganda, Rwanda, Kenya, Tanzania, Ethiopia

Epilachna karisimbica (Weise, 1912)

Distribution: Zaire, Uganda, North Rwanda

Epilachna kivuensis Fursch, 1963

Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna konsoensis Jadwiszczak, 2003

Distribution: Ethiopia

Epilachna korschefskyi (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire, Rwanda

Epilachna kraatzi (Weise, 1898)

Distribution: Cameroon, Guinea

Epilachna kraussi Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Panama Colombia

Epilachna kreissli Fursch, 1963

Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna lacordairii Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna laesicollis Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: India (Darjeeling, Sikkim), Nepal

Epilachna langpingensis Zeng et Yang, 1996

Distribution: China

Epilachna languida (Weise, 1900)

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna laosana (Bielawski, 1960)

Distribution: India, Laos, Vietnam

Epilachna lasioides (Ricard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna lata Li in Li et Cook, 1961

Distribution: Taiwan

Epilachna lateripicta Fairmaire, 1889

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna latesellata (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna lateumerosa Fursch, 1987

Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna laticollis (Weise, 1899)

Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna latimargo (Weise, 1926)

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna latipennis (Korschefsky, 1929)

Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna latreillei Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna lenta (Weise, 1902)

Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna lepida Erichson, 1847

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna lesnei (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna lichunaniensis Xiao in Xiao et Li, 1992

Distribution: China (Hubei)

Epilachna linnaei Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Republic of South Africa

Epilachna loculosa Sicard, 1913

Distribution: South India

Epilachna longissima (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Taiwan

Epilachna lorata Weise, 1895

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna lothi Jadwiszczak, 2003

Distribution: Republic of South Africa

Epilachna loveni (Weise, 1926)

Distribution: Uganda, Rwanda

Epilachna lugubris (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: China

Epilachna luluensis Fursch, 1985

Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna lupina Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Ethiopia, Uganda, Zaire, Kenya, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, Mozambique, South Africa

Epilachna lurida (Korschefsky, 1928)

Distribution: Uganda, Rwanda

Epilachna luteocincta (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna macquarti Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna macularis Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: India, Nepal, China

Epilachna maculicollis (Sicard, 1912)

Distribution: Taiwan

Epilachna maculivestis Mulsant, 1853

Distribution: India, Nepal, China (Tibet)

Epilachna madida Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Venezuela, Colombia

Epilachna madrigali Gordon, 1985

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna magna (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: China

Epilachna magnomaculata (Fursch, 1960)

Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna malleforma Peng in Peng et Ren, 2002

Distribution: China

Epilachna mammifera Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna mandibularis Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna manni Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna margaritifera Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna marginella (Fabricius, 1787)

Distribution: Brazil

Epilachna marginicollis (Hope, 1831)

Distribution: India (Sikkim, North Bengal), Nepal, Bhutan, Burma

Epilachna mausmainesis Jadwiszczak, 1990

Distribution: India (Assam)

Epilachna maxima (Weise, 1898)

Distribution: India (Assam), China, Taiwan, Vietnam

Epilachna media Li in Li et Cook, 1961

Distribution: Taiwan

Epilachna medvedevi Hoang, 1978

Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna melanocephala Hoang, 1978

Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna meleagris (Klug, 1833)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna merae Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna merkli Fursch, 1987

Distribution: Malawi

Epilachna mermoides Fursch 19897

Distribution: Ruwenzori Mts. (Uganda/Zaire)

Epilachna mexicana (Guerin-Meneville, 1844)

Distribution: Mexico, Costa Rica, Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, Nicaragua, Panama, Venezuela, Colombia

Epilachna microgenitalia Li in Li et Cook, 1961

Distribution: China, Taiwan

Epilachna militaris (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: India, Nepal

Epilachna minuta Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna mirabilis (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Tanzania, Zaire

Epilachna mirabiloides (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: China, Vietnam

Epilachna mirifica (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire, Tanzania

Epilachna misella Weise, 1897

Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna mobiliteriae Li in Li et Cook, 1961
Distribution: Taiwan

Epilachna modesta Mulsant, 1850
Distribution: Mexico

Epilachna moesta Gistel, 1848
Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna monovittata Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Colombia, Peru

Epilachna monsuna Bielawski, 1979
Distribution: Bhutan

Epilachna montana Hoang, 1978
Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna moorii Crotch, 1974
Distribution: India (Darjeeling)

Epilachna morbida (Weise, 1919)
Distribution: Zaire, Rwanda

Epilachna morbidoides (Mader, 1955)
Distribution: Zaire, Rwanda

Epilachna morogoroensis Fursch, 1985
Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna mushana Li in Li et Cook, 1961
Distribution: Taiwan

Epilachna mutabilis Crotch, 1874
Distribution: Ecuador, Peru

Epilachna mystica Mulsant, 1850
Distribution: Northern India, Nepal, Bhutan, Burma

Epilachna nantai (Sicard, 1907)
Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna narinoi Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna nepalensis (Kapur, 1958)
Distribution: Nepal

Epilachna nevillei Dohrn, 1880

Distribution: Andaman Is.

Epilachna ngheanensis Hoang, 1978

Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna nielamuensis Pang et Mao, 1977

Distribution: China (Tibet), Nepal

Epilachna nigeriana (Mader, 1958)

Distribution: Nigeria, Cameroon

Epilachna nigripes Weise, 1895

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna nigratarsis Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Senegal, Togo, Sierra Leone, Ivory Coast, Cameroon, Uganda

Epilachna nigrocincta Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Mexico, Guatemala

Epilachna nigrolimbata J. Thomson, 1858

Distribution: Equatorial Guinea (Fernando Poo Is.), Cameroon

Epilachna nigromarginata Fursch, 1963

Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna nigrotincta (Mader, 1957)

Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna nigrovittata Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna nilgirica (Weise, 1908)

Distribution: Southern India

Epilachna nonveilleri Fursch, 1986

Distribution: Guiana, Cameroon

Epilachna novemdecimguttata (Weise, 1903)

Distribution: Cameroon, Zaire, Uganda, Rwanda, Kenya

Epilachna novenaria Mulsant, 1872

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna nudiuscula (Weise, 1909)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna nylanderi Mulsant, 1850
Distribution: Republic of South Africa

Epilachna oberthueri Weise, 1895
Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna obliqua Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Peru

Epilachna obscurella Mulsant 1850
Distribution: Mexico

Epilachna obscuritarsis (Sicard, 1907)
Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna obsoleta (Olivier, 1808)
Distribution: Madagascar, Mozambique

Epilachna obtusiforma Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna occidentalis Crotch, 1874
Distribution: Sierra Leone, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Congo

Epilachna ocellataemaculata (Mader, 1930)
Distribution: China, Vietnam

Epilachna ocreata Zeng et Yang, 1996
Distribution: China (Guanxi)

Epilachna octodecimsignata Weise, 1895
Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna octomaculata (Thunberg, 1781)
Distribution: Burma

Epilachna octoverrucata Mulsant, 1850
Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna olivacea Mulsant 1850
Distribution: Mexico, Guatemala, Costa Rica

Epilachna olmosi Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Peru

Epilachna orthofasciata (Dieke, 1947)
Distribution: Indonesia (Java)

Epilachna orthostriata Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna ostensa (Weise, 1902)

Distribution: Peru, Bolivia

Epilachna ostensoides Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Ecuador, Peru

Epilachna ovaloides Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna oviforma Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna pachiteensis (Weise, 1926)

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna paenulata (Germar, 1824)

Distribution: Colombia, Ecuador, Peru, Bolivia, Paraguay, Uruguay, Argentina, Brazil

Epilachna paling Yu, 2001

Distribution: Taiwan

Epilachna paracuta Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna paradoxa (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire, Tanzania, Rwanda

Epilachna parainsignis Pang et Mao, 1979

Distribution: China

Epilachna paramagna Pang et Mao, 1979

Distribution: China

Epilachna parastriata Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna parvicollis Casey, 1899

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna pastica (Weise, 1902)

Distribution: Peru Bolivia

Epilachna patricia Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Peru, Bolivia, Argentina

Epilachna patula Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Mexico

Epilachna pava Weise, 1895

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna pavonia (Olivier, 1808)

Distribution: Madagascar, Comoro Is.

Epilachna paykullii Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Cameroon, Zaire, Kenya, Tanzania (including Zanzibar), Madagascar

Epilachna pellita Fursch, 1987

Distribution: Kenya, Burundi

Epilachna peltata Erichson, 1847

Distribution: Peru, Bolivia

Epilachna pembertoni Crotch, 1874

Distribution: India, Bhutan

Epilachna pemptea Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna perlata (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna persimilis Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Ecuador, Peru

Epilachna pertyi Crotch, 18874

Distribution: Brazil

Epilachna peruviana Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna picta (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna picticollis (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna pictipennis Crotch 1874

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna pierreti (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna pingbianensis Pang et Mao, 1979

Distribution: China

Epilachna plagiata Gorham, 1897

Distribution: Costa Rica, Panama

Epilachna planimarginata Fursch, 1963

Distribution: Ethiopia

Epilachna plicata Weise, 1889

Distribution: China

Epilachna pocohantae Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Mexico, Guatemala, Salvador, Costa Rica, Panama

Epilachna pondoensis Fursch, 1987

Distribution: Republic of South Africa

Epilachna praecipua Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna pretiosa (Mader, 1958)

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna probsti Jadwiszczak et Putz, 1994

Distribution: Southern India

Epilachna propinqua (Weise, 1900)

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna provisoria (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: China

Epilachna pseudograptia Gordon, 19975

Distribution: Costa Rica

Epilachna pseudokraatzi Fursch, 1987

Distribution: East Africa (Lomami, Kaniama)

Epilachna pseudolepida Gordon, 1986

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna pseudorealis Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Panama, Colombia

Epilachna pseudospilota Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna pseudostrata Gordon, 1975
Distribution Peru

Epilachna pseudotumida Gordon, 1985
Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna punctatissima (Weise, 1904)
Distribution: Argentina

Epilachna punctipennis Mulsant, 1850
Distribution: Guinea, Uganda, Togo, Tanzania

Epilachna pusilla Fursch, 1963
Distributon: Tanzania, Zaire

Epilachna quadricollis (Dieke, 1947)
Distribution: Korea, China, Taiwan

Epilachna quadriguttula (Mader, 1941)
Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna quadripunctata (Weise, 1905)
Distributon: Madagascar

Epilachna quangbinhensis Hoang, 1978
Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna quatuordecimpunctata (Mader, 1941)
Distribution: Rwanda, Zaire

Epilachna quichauensis Hoang, 1978
Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna quinquedecimpunctata (Mader, 1941)
Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna quirozensis Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Peru

Epilachna radiata (Guerin-Meneville, 1844)
Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna rauli Gordon, 1985
Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna reichei Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Colombia, Ecuador

Epilachna renati Ricard, 1907

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna reticulipennis Fursch, 1985

Distribution: Republic of South Africa

Epilachna riveti (Sicard, 1911)

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna rubiacis Cao et Xiao, 1984

Distribution: China

Epilachna rubida Fursch, 2001

Distribution: Kenya

Epilachna rubicollis (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna rudepunctata Mader, 1957

Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna rufolonga Fursch, 1985

Distribution: Sudan

Epilachna rufonotata Fursch, 1986

Distribution: Cameroon

Epilachna ryszardi Jadwiszczak, 2003

Distribution: Bhutan

Epilachna saginata (Weise, 1902)

Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna sahlbergi Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: East and South Africa

Epilachna satipennis Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna sauteri (Weise, 1923)

Distribution: China, Taiwan, Japan (Okinawa Is.)

Epilachna schawalleri Canepari, 1997

Distribution: Nepal

Epilachna schoenherri Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Republic of South Africa

Epilachna schoutedeni (Sicard, 1930)

Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna schunkei Gordoan, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna sellata Weise, 1895

Distribution: Peru, Bolivia, Argentina

Epilachna septemnotata Bielawski, 1979

Distribution: Bhutan

Epilachna septemocellata Sigh et Singh, 1990

Distribution: India

Epilachna septentrionalis Fursch, 1963

Distribution: Sudan

Epilachna seria (Weise, 1898)

Distribution: Equatorial Guiana (Fernando Poo Is.), Congo, Cameroon

Epilachna severini Weise, 1900

Distribution: Cameroon

Epilachna sexguttata (Weise, 1899)

Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna sexlineata (Weise, 1898)

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna sexmaculata Kirsch, 1876

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna sexpunctata Bielawski, 1979

Distribution: Bhutan

Epilachna sexpustulata Bielawski, 1979

Distribution: Bhutan

Epilachna shilliensis Singh et Singh, 1990

Distribution: India

Epilachna shimbaensis Fursch, 1985

Distribution: Kenya

Epilachna signifera (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna simia (Sicard, 1913)

Distribution: Southern India

Epilachna simulans Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna simulatrix (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna sinuata (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna siphodontulata Hoang, 1978

Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna siphonechinulata Zeng et Yang, 1996

Distribution: China (Guangxi)

Epilachna smithi Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Republic of South Africa

Epilachna soachae Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna soarezica (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna sociolamina Li in Li et Cook, 1961

Distribution: Taiwan

Epilachna soluta (Weise, 1900)

Distribution: Kenya, Tanzania

Epilachna spinolae Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna spiraloides Cao et Xiao, 1984

Distribution: China

Epilachna spreta Mulsant 1850

Distribution: Brazil

Epilachna staudingeri (Weise, 1902)

Distribution: Peru, Bolivia

Epilachna stolata Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Venezuela

Epilachna stragulata Fursch, 1963
Distribution: Kenya

Epilachna strasseni Fursch, 1963
Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna strictanotata Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Peru

Epilachna striola (Weise, 1902)
Distribution: Peru

Epilachna struwei Fursch, 2001
Distribution: Rwanda

Epilachna subacuta (Dieke, 1947)
Distribution: China

Epilachna subclathrata Sicard, 1910
Distribution: Southern India

Epilachna superba (Mader, 1955)
Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna sureilica (Kapur, 1963)
Distribution: India, Burma

Epilachna suspiciosa Weise, 1901
Distribution: India (Darjeeling Sikkim)

Epilachna suturoguttata Fursch, 1991
Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna szechuana (Dieke, 1947)
Distribution: China

Epilachna sztolcmani Jadwiszczak, 2003
Distribution: Peru

Epilachna taeniola Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna tanalensis (Sicard, 1907)
Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna tenebricosa Mulsant, 1850
Distribution: Mexico

Epilachna tenella (Sicard, 1930)

Distribution: Angola, Cameroon, Zaire, Rwanda

Epilachna tenelloides (Fursch, 1960)

Distribution: Tanzania, Rwanda, Kenya

Epilachna tenuepicta (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna tetartea Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna tetrastigma (Weise, 1912)

Distribution: North Rwanda

Epilachna tianpingiensis Pang et Mao, 1979

Distribution: China

Epilachna tibialis Weise, 1888

Distribution: South and West Africa

Epilachna togoensis (Weise, 1901)

Distribution: Togo, Guinea

Epilachna topali Jadwischczak, 1990

Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna transverselineata (Mader, 1958)

Distribution: Peru, Bolivia

Epilachna tredecimnotata (Latreille, 1833)

Distribution: USA, Mexico, Cuba, Guatemala, Belize, Salvador, Honduras, Nicaragua, Costa Rica, Panama, Venezuela, Colombia

Epilachna tricolor (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna tridecimmaculosa Pang et Mao, 1977

Distribution: China

Epilachna tridivisa Hoang, 1978

Distribution: Vietnam

Epilachna trifaria (Weise, 1899)

Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna tripupillata (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna tristis Gorham, 1897

Distribution: Mexico

Epilachna tritea Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Venezuela

Epilachna trochula Fursch, 1991

Distribution: Republic of South Africa

Epilachna tshibindaensis Jadwiszczak, 2003

Distribution: Zaire, Tanzania

Epilachna tumida Gorham 1897

Distribution: Costa Rica, Panama

Epilachna uhligi Fursch, 19987

Distribution: Tanzania

Epilachna umerata Fursch, 1963

Distribution: Kenya

Epilachna undecimspilota (Hope, 1831)

Distribution: Northern India, Nepal

Epilachna undulata (Thunberg, 1781)

Distribution: Republic of South Africa

Epilachna univittata Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Ecuador

Epilachna urundiensis Fursch, 1963

Distribution: Rwanda, Burundi

Epilachna vagula Fursch, 1963

Distribution: Tanzania (including Zanzibar), Uganda

Epilachna vanpatteni Gorham, 1898

Distribution: Guatemala, Costa Rica

Epilachna varipes Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Mexico

Epilachna varivestis Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: USA, Mexico, Guatemala, Honduras, Salvador, Costa Rica

Epilachna velata Erichson, 1847

Distribution: Peru Bolivia

Epilachna velutina (Olivier, 1808)

Distribution: Surinam, French Guiana

Epilachna venterita Fursch, 1975

Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna vermiculata (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Madagascar

Epilachna vigintiduomaculata (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire, Uganda, Tanzania

Epilachna vigintiduopunctata (Mader, 1957)

Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna vigintipunctata Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Guinea, Angola, Rwanda, Ethiopia, Kenya, Tanzania (including Zanzibar), Mozambique, Republic of South Africa

Epilachna villica Weise, 1888

Distribution: Guinea, Ivory Coast, Togo, Nigeria, Cameroon, Gabon, Congo, Zaire

Epilachna vincta Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Mexico, Guatemala, Belize, Costa Rica

Epilachna viridilineata Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Ecuador, Peru

Epilachna viridinitens Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Peru

Epilachna vittigera Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Peru, Bolivia

Epilachna v-pallidum Blanchard in Blanchard et Brulle, 1846

Distribution: Peru, Bolivia

Epilachna vulcanica (Weise, 1912)

Distribution: Northern Rwanda, Uganda

Epilachna vulnerata Gorham, 1898

Distribution: Mexico, Guatemala

Epilachna vulpecula Reiche, 1849

Distribution: Ethiopia, Uganda, Kenya, Rwanda, Tanzania

Epilachna walteri (Sicard, 1913)

Distribution: Colombia

Epilachna wisei (Sicard, 1912)

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna wernerii Fursch, 1985

Distribution: Rwanda

Epilachna witteiana (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire

Epilachna woytkowskii Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru, Bolivia

Epilachna yongshanensis Cao et Xiao, 1984

Distribution: China (Yunnan)

Epilachna zetterstedtii Mulsant, 1850

Distribution: Tanzania, Republic of South Africa

Epilachna zeylanica Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Sri Lanka

Epilachna zischkai (Mader, 1950)

Distribution: Bolivia

Epilachna zuluensis Crotch, 1874

Distribution: Zaire, Rwanda, Burundi, Tanzania

Epilachna zumpti Fursch, 1963

Distribution: East Africa, Tanzania

Genus ***Henosepilachna*** Li in Li et Cook, 1961

Henosepilachna acervata Chazeau, 1975

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna adjuncta (Crotch, 1874)

Distribution: Angola

Henosepilachna aegrota (Gorham, 1891)

Distribution: Ethiopia

Henosepilachna altera (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Philippines, Fiji Is.

Henosepilachna alternata (Sicard, 1930)

Distribution: Zaire, Uganda, Kenya, Tanzania

Henosepilachna ambitiosa (Mader, 1955)

Distribution: Cameroon

Henosepilachna amoena (Karsch, 1882)

Distribution: Angola, Cameroon, Zaire

Henosepilachna animanigra Chazeau, 1975

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna anita (Kapur, 1952)

Distribution: South India

Henosepilachna annulata (Kolbe, 1897)

Distribution: Central and South Africa

Henosepilachna annulifera (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire

Henosepilachna antinorii (Gorham, 1891)

Distribution: Sudan, Ethiopia

Henosepilachna antiqua (Weise, 1903)

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna apicalis (Weise, 1898)

Distribution: Cameroon, Togo, Sierra Leone

Henosepilachna ardosiacae (Sicard, 1912)

Distribution: Zimbabwe

Henosepilachna arenaria (Weise, 1914)

Distribution: Namibia

Henosepilachna argus (Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785)

Distribution: Central and South Europe, North Africa

Henosepilachna atra (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Kenya, Uganda

Henosepilachna atropos (Sicard, 1912)

Distribution: Equatorial Guinea (Fernando Poo Is.)

Henosepilachna auroguttata (Weise, 1895)

Distribution: Togo, Zaire, Tanzania

Henosepilachna bachtaiensis Hoang, 1977

Distribution: Vietnam

Henosepilachna baguiana (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Philippines

Henosepilachna balajuensis (Jadwiszczak et Putz, 1994)

Distribution: Nepal

Henosepilachna bakeri (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Philippines

Henosepilachna bielawskii (Fursch, 1959)

Distribution: South India

Henosepilachna bifasciata (Fabricius, 1781)

Distribution: Indonesia (Java)

Henosepilachna bigemmata Fursch, 1991

Distribution: Cameroon

Henosepilachna biplagiata (Kolbe, 1897)

Distribution: Cameroon, Zaire, Rwanda, Uganda, Kenya, Tanzania

Henosepilachna bipunctata (Weise, 1905)

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna biroi (Weise, 1902)

Distribution: New Guinea, New Britain, Philippines

Henosepilachna bisdecemnotata (Weise, 1905)

Distribution: Zaire, Uganda, Rwanda, Tanzania

Henosepilachna bisquadrisingnata (Mader, 1958)

Distribution: Cameroon

Henosepilachna bisseptemnotata (Mulsant, 1853)

Distribution: Ethiopia, Kenya, Uganda, Rwanda, Tanzania

Henosepilachna blanchardi (Fauvel, 1862)

Distribution: New Caledonia

Henosepilachna boisduvali (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: India, China, Taiwan, Vietnam, Lan Yu Is., Philippines, Indonesia, New Guinea, Samoa Is, New Hebrides, Fiji Is., Australia

Henosepilachna bona Bielawski, 1965

Distribution: New Ireland

Henosepilachna buehleri (Bielawski, 1959)

Distribution: Indonesia (Flores Is.)

Henosepilachna buqueti (Moontrouzier, 1861)

Distribution: New Caledonia (Art Is.), Fiji Is.

Henosepilachna callipepla (Gerstaecker, 1871)

Distribution: Tanzania (including Zanzibar), Kenya, Madagascar

Henosepilachna capensis (Thunberg, 1781)

Distribution: Republic of South Africa

Henosepilachna chenoni (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Guinea, Ghana, Togo, Equatorial Guinea, Cameroon, Congo, Angola, Zaire, Tanzania, Kenya

Henosepilachna chirindica (Sicard, 1912)

Distribution: Namibia, Zimbabwe, Republic of South Africa

Henosepilachna chromata Fursch, 1991

Distribution: Cameroon, Rwanda

Henosepilachna cinerascens (Weise, 1907)

Distribution: Ethiopia

Henosepilachna circellaris (Weise, 1908)

Distribution: India

Henosepilachna circularis (Korschefsky, 1934)

Distribution: India

Henosepilachna clavareau (Weise, 1901)

Distribution: Cameroon, Angola, Tanzania, Zaire

Henosepilachna congoana (Mader, 1957)

Distribution: Zaire

Henosepilachna congrex (Weise, 1909)

Distribution: Ethiopia

Henosepilachna connectens (Weise, 1912)

Distribution: Rwanda, Zaire

Henosepilachna cruxaustralis Chazeau, 1975

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna cuprina (Weise, 1906)

Distribution: Tanzania

Henosepilachna curvisignata (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Rwanda, Zaire

Henosepilachna depauperata (Mader, 1957)

Distribution: Zaire

Henosepilachna descarpentriasi Chazeau, 1975

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna diffinis (Eydoux et Souleyet, 1839)

Distribution: Philippines (Palawan), Indonesia (Borneo, Java)

Henosepilachna discreta (Weise, 1909)

Distribution: Cameroon, Zaire, Rwanda, Tanzania

Henosepilachna diversa (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Philippines

Henosepilachna dodecastigma (Wiedemann, 1823)

Distribution: India/Bangladesh

Henosepilachna donendrina Chazeau, 1976

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna dubiosa (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: India, Indonesia (Borneo)

Henosepilachna duodecimguttata (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire, Tanzania

Henosepilachna duodecimmaculata (Thunberg, 1820)

Distribution: Asia

Henosepilachna elaterii (Rossi, 1794)

Distribution: South Europe, Turkey, North Africa, Sudan, Senegal, Tschad, Niger, Volta, Iran
Iraq, Afghanistan, Pakistan

Henosepilachna elongata (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Philippines

Henosepilachna enneasticta (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Indonesia (Sumatra, Java)

Henosepilachna erichi (Weise, 1897)

Distribution: Uganda, Tanzania

Henosepilachna erlangeri (Weise, 1907)

Distribution: Ethiopia

Henosepilachna ertli (Weise, 1906)

Distribution: Cameroon, Equatorial Guinea, Zaire, Uganda, Tanzania, Ethiopia

Henosepilachna eudoxa (Weise, 1907)

Distribution: Ethiopia

Henosepilachna extraordinaria Fursch, 1975

Distribution: Zaire

Henosepilachna fabriciana (Korschefsky, 1931)

Distribution: Central, East and South Africa

Henosepilachna firma (Weise, 1900)

Distribution: Tanzania, Republic of South Africa

Henosepilachna flavipalpis (Weise, 1898)

Distribution: Tanzania

Henosepilachna fuerschi Jadwischczak, 2003

Distribution: Philippines (Luzon)

Henosepilachna fulvimana (Weise, 1903)

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna fulvosignata (Reiche, 1849)

Distribution: Ethiopia

Henosepilachna gangetica (Weise, 1908)

Distribution: India, Vietnam

Henosepilachna gemmifera (Arrow, 1909)

Distribution: Uganda

Henosepilachna genitalis Hoang, 1977

Distribution: Vietnam

Henosepilachna gibba (Thunberg, 1781)

Distribution: Zaire, Kenya, Tanzania

Henosepilachna griveaudi Chazeau, 1975

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna guineensis (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Sierra Leone, Ivory Coast, Togo, Nigeria, Cameroon, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon

Henosepilachna guttatopustulata (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution: New Guinea, Bismarck Is., Solomon Is., Australia, New Hebrides

Henosepilachna guttifera (Weise, 1899)

Distribution: Zaire, Uganda, Tanzania

Henosepilachna hades Chazeau, 1975

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna haematomelas (Boisduval, 1835)

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna haemorrhoea (Boisduval, 1835)

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna hanoiensis Hoang, 1977

Distribution: Vietnam

Henosepilachna hauseri (Weise, 1904)

Distribution: Tanzania

Henosepilachna hemispherica (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Philippines

Henosepilachna hilaris (Mader, 1957)

Distribution: Zaire

Henosepilachna hintzi (Weise, 1901)

Distribution: Tanzania, Kenya

Henosepilachna hirta (Thunberg, 1781)

Distribution: Cameroon, Angola, Zaire, Ethiopia, Kenya, Tanzania, Mozambique, Republic of South Africa, Madagascar

Henosepilachna hirtaeformis (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire, Rwanda

Henosepilachna humerosa (Weise, 1905)

Distribution: Zaire, Rwanda, Kenya

Henosepilachna huonensis (Bielawski, 1963)

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna hypocrita Fursch, 1991

Distribution: Rwanda

Henosepilachna immaculata (Bielawski, 1963)

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna implicata (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: India

Henosepilachna indica (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Nepal, India (Sikkim, Assam), Vietnam, Burma, Laos, China

Henosepilachna indistincta (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Indonesia (Sumatra)

Henosepilachna johanna (Weise, 1897)

Distribution: Tanzania, Zaire

Henosepilachna kabakovi Hoang, 1977

Distribution: Vietnam

Henosepilachna kaesebergi (Weise, 1898)

Distribution: Zaire, Rwanda

Henosepilachna kaffaeensis (Weise, 1906)

Distribution: Ethiopia, Kenya, Rwanda, Zaire, Uganda

Henosepilachna kampeni (Weise, 1917)

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna karapensis (Bielawski, 1963)

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna karenensis (Kapur, 1961)

Distribution: Burma

Henosepilachna kaszabi (Bielawski et Fursch, 1960)

Distribution: Burma, Vietnam, China, India, Andaman Is., Philippines

Henosepilachna kathmanduensis Miyatake, 1985

Distribution: Nepal

Henosepilachna khasiensis (Weise, 1901)

Distribution: India (Assam)

Henosepilachna kiboensis Jadwischczak, 2003

Distribution: Tanzania, Kenya

Henosepilachna labyrinthica (Weise, 1904)

Distribution: Kenya, Tanzania

Henosepilachna lanceolata (Sicard, 1912)

Distribution: Zaire, Kenya, Tanzania, Zimbabwe

Henosepilachna laokayensis Hoang, 1977

Distribution: Vietnam

Henosepilachna leucosticta (Weise, 1912)

Distribution: Tanzania, Zaire, Rwanda, Uganda

Henosepilachna libera (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: China, Taiwan

Henosepilachna loennbergi (Weise, 1926)

Distribution: Kenya, Zaire, Tanzania

Henosepilachna lucifera (Arrow, 1909)

Distribution: Zaire, Uganda, Rwanda

Henosepilachna luteoguttata (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Egypt, Sudan, Somalia, Mozambique

Henosepilachna luzonica (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Philippines

Henosepilachna mafula (Bielawski, 1963)

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna mamitaka Chazeau, 1976

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna manipurensis (Kapur, 1952)

Distribution: India (Assam)

Henosepilachna maunsonica Jadwischczak, 2003

Distribution: Vietnam

Henosepilachna mediodentata (Bielawski, 1963)

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna meretricula Chazeau, 1975

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna mindanaonis (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Philippines

Henosepilachna mjoebergi (Weise, 1923)

Distribution: Australia

Henosepilachna morosa (Weise, 1900)

Distribution: Tanzania, Zanzibar, Zimbabwe

Henosepilachna moseri (Weise, 1903)

Distribution: Equatorial Guinea (Fernando Poo, Is.), Cameroon

Henosepilachna mucronata (Korschefsky, 1928)

Distribution: Uganda, Zaire, Tanzania (including Zanzibar)

Henosepilachna murrayi (Crotch, 1874)

Distribution: Guinea, Ivory Coast, Ghana, Cameroon, Equatorial Guinea (Fernando Poo, Is.), Congo, Zaire

Henosepilachna musosaensis Fursch, 1991

Distribution: Zaire

Henosepilachna mutata Fursch, 1991

Distribution: Cameroon, Zaire

Henosepilachna nana (Kapur, 1952)

Distribution: South India

Henosepilachna narayana (Lal et Kanakavalli, 1961)

Distribution: India

Henosepilachna natalensis (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: South Africa

Henosepilachna nativitatis (Arrow in Waterhouse, Gahan et Arrow, 1900)

Distribution: Christmas Is.

Henosepilachna neumanni (Weise, 1907)

Distribution: Ethiopia

Henosepilachna niponica (Lewis, 1896)

Distribution: Japan

Henosepilachna novemmaculata (Korschefsky, 1935)

Distribution: Cameroon, Angola, Zaire

Henosepilachna nympa (Arrow, 1909)

Distribution: Zaire, Rwanda, Uganda

Henosepilachna obliterated (Weise, 1898)

Distribution: Cameroon

Henosepilachna ocellata (Bertoloni, 1849)

Distribution: Ethiopia, Burundi, Kenya, Tanzania (including Zanzibar), Mozambique

Henosepilachna oceanica (Bielawski, 1963)

Distribution: Aru Is., Christmas Is.

Henosepilachna ocellata (Redtenbacher in Kollar et Redtenbacher, 1844)

Distribution: Noth India, Nepal, China

Henosepilachna ochatra Chazeau, 1976

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna operculata (Liu, 1950)

Distribution: China

Henosepilachna ornata (Kapur, 1963)

Distribution: India

Henosepilachna orrori (Bielawski, 1963)

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna pagana (Mulsant, 1853)

Distribution: Indonesia (Java)

Henosepilachna parda Fursch, 1991

Distribution: Cameroon, Zaire, Burundi

Henosepilachna pauli (Weise, 1897)

Distribution: Tanzania

Henosepilachna perplexa (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: India, Thailand

Henosepilachna peyrrierasi Chazeau, 1975

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna popei Fursch, 1991

Distribution: Uganda

Henosepilachna processa Li et Cook, 1961

Distribution: China, Taiwan, Vietnam

Henosepilachna pusillanima (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: India, Nepal, China, Taiwan, Thailand, Vietnam, Philippines, Indonesia

Henosepilachna pustulosa (Kono, 1937)

Distribution: Japan

Henosepilachna pytharga (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Taiwan, Philippines (Luzon)

Henosepilachna pytho (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Indonesia (Java, Sumatra), Burma, Philippines

Henosepilachna quadriguttata (Weise, 1897)

Distribution: Tanzania

Henosepilachna quadrioculata (Kolbe, 1897)

Distribution: Sudan, Zaire, Uganda, Rwanda, Kenya, Tanzania, Zimbabwe

Henosepilachna quadripartita (Weise, 1912)

Distribution: Uganda, Zaire, Tanzania

Henosepilachna quadriplagiata Pang et Mao, 1977

Distribution: China

Henosepilachna quarta (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: India

Henosepilachna quatuordecimsignata (Reiche, 1849)

Distribution: Cameroon, Ethiopia, Uganda, Zaire, Tanzania (including Zanzibar)

Henosepilachna quinta (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Sri Lanka

Henosepilachna raharizoninai Chazeau, 1975

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna randriamasyi Chazeau, 1977

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna reducta (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Philippines

Henosepilachna regina (Weise, 1898)

Distribution: Tanzania

Henosepilachna reticulata (Olivier, 1791)

Distribution: Senegal, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Sierra Leone, Ivory Coast, Cameroon, Angola, Zaire, Congo, Uganda, Kenya, Sudan, Ethiopia

Henosepilachna retigera (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: East Africa

Henosepilachna rothschildi (Sicard, 1907)

Distribution: Kenya

Henosepilachna rudepunctata Fursch, 1964

Distribution: Zaire

Henosepilachna rudis (Weise, 1907)

Distribution: Ethiopia

Henosepilachna rufociliata Hoang, 1977

Distribution: Vietnam

Henosepilachna ruvenzorica Jadwiszczak, 2003

Distribution: Uganda, Kenya

Henosepilachna samuelsoni (Jadwiszczak, 1991)

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna satanas (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire, Kenya

Henosepilachna scalaroides Fursch, 1991

Distribution: Uganda, Rwanda

Henosepilachna schultzei Bielawski, 1965

Distribution: Philippines

Henosepilachna scutellaris (Kolbe, 1897)

Distribution: Zaire, Rwanda, Uganda, Kenya

Henosepilachna sedecimverrucata (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Guinea, Ivory Coast, Cameroon

Henosepilachna septima (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Vietnam, Sri Lanka, India

Henosepilachna sericata (Weise, 1898)

Distribution: Tanzania

Henosepilachna sexsignata (Mader, 1957)

Distribution: Zaire

Henosepilachna sexta (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Indonesia (Celebes)

Henosepilachna signatipennis (Boisduval, 1835)

Distribution: New Guinea, New Britain, New Ireland, Solomon Is.

Henosepilachna sikkimica (Kapur, 1963)

Distribution: India (Sikkim)

Henosepilachna simplex (Weise, 1895)

Distribution: Sierra Leone

Henosepilachna singularis (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire

Henosepilachna slipinskii (Jadwiszczak, 1987)

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna sobrina (Harold, 1874)

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna socialis (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: SE Asia

Henosepilachna sogai Chazeau, 1975

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna solomonensis (Dieke, 1947)

Distribution: Solomon Is.

Henosepilachna soror (Weise, 1897)

Distribution: Tanzania

Henosepilachna stanleyi Bielawski, 1972

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna subfasciata (Weise, 1923)

Distribution: Taiwan

Henosepilachna subnigra (Bielawski, 1963)

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna suffusa (Crotch, 1874)

Distribution: Australia

Henosepilachna sumatrensis (Fursch, 1959)

Distribution: Indonesia (Sumatra), Philippines

Henosepilachna sumbana (Bielawski, 1959)

Distribution: Philippines, Indonesia (Timor), Australia, New Guinea, Samoa, New Caledonia, New Britain, Manus Is., Solomon Is., Ceram Is., Kai., Aru Is., Maluku, Amboina

Henosepilachna sutteri (Bielawski, 1959)

Distribution: Indonesia (Sumba Is.)

Henosepilachna taeniata (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Indonesia (Java)

Henosepilachna tahaka Chazeau 1976

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna tamdaoensis Hoang, 1977

Distribution: Vietnam

Henosepilachna tarda (Weise, 1900)

Distribution: Tanzania

Henosepilachna tenua Fursch, 1964

Distribution: Zaire

Henosepilachna tetracycla (Gerstaecker, 1871)

Distribution: Zaire, Uganda, Rwanda, Somalia, Tanzania, Kenya

Henosepilachna tetragramma (Weise, 1912)

Distribution: Uganda

Henosepilachna tonkinensis (Bielawski, 1957)

Distribution: South China, Vietnam

Henosepilachna tremula Chazeau 1975

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna tricolorata Fursch, 1991

Distribution: Republic of South Africa

Henosepilachna triquetra (Weise, 1904)

Distribution: Cameroon, Zaire, Kenya, Tanzania, Malawi

Henosepilachna tsara Chazeau, 1975

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna umbonata Pang et Mao, 1979

Distribution: China

Henosepilachna umbratilis (Weise, 1909)

Distribution: Tanzania

Henosepilachna undecimmaculata (Fabricius, 1787)

Distribution: Spain, France

Henosepilachna undecimsignata (Thunberg, 1820)

Distribution: Asia

Henosepilachna undecimvariolata (Boisduval, 1835)

Distribution: Indonesia (Celebes, Sumba, Flores, Timor), Kawongoa, New Guinea, Australia (Tasmania)

Henosepilachna unidentata (Bielawski, 1963)

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna urvillei (Montrouzier, 1862)

Distribution: New Guinea, Solomon Is., Loyalty Is., Australia

Henosepilachna vadoni Chazeau 1976

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna verriculata Pang et Mao, 1979

Distribution: China (Yunnan)

Henosepilachna versuta (Weise, 1903)

Distribution: Cameroon

Henosepilachna vicaria (Weise, 1909)

Distribution: Tanzania

Henosepilachna victoria Chazeau, 1975

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna viettei Chazeau, 1975

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna vigintioctomaculata (Motschulsky, 1857)

Distribution: Russian Far East (Primorski Krai, Khabarovsk Krai), Japan, Korea, China, Taiwan, Vietnam, Nepal

Henosepilachna vigintioctopunctata (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution: Pakistan, India, Sri Lanka, Japan, China, Taiwan, Nepal, Bhutan, Burma, Thailand, Vietnam, Philippines, Indonesia, New Guinea, Fiji, Solomon Is., Australia

Henosepilachna vigintisexpunctata (Boisduval, 1835)

Distribution: Philippines, Vietnam, Timor, New Guinea, Solomon, Is., Australia

Henosepilachna vittula (Weise, 1897)

Distribution: Tanzania, Kenya

Henosepilachna vulgaris (Weise, 1901)

Distribution: Gabon, Cameroon

Henosepilachna waerebekei Chazaeau 1977

Distribution: Madagascar

Henosepilachna wanati (Jadwiszczak, 1986)

Distribution: New Guinea

Henosepilachna warchalowskii (Jadwiszczak, 1990)

Distribution: Vietnam

Henosepilachna wissmanni (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Philippines, Indonesia (Borneo, Celebes, Sumatra)

Henosepilachna yamuna (Mulsant, 1853)

Distribution: Indonesia (Java)

Henosepilachna yasutomii Katakura, 1981

Distribution: Japan

Henosepilachna zebra Jadwiszczak, 2003

Distribution: South India

Henosepilachna zenkeri (Weise, 1898)

Distribution: Cameroon

Genus ***Macrolasia*** Weise, 1903

Macrolasia arcula Weise, 1903

Distribution: India

Genus ***Subafissa*** Bielawski, 1963

Subafissa brittoni Bielawski, 1963

Distribution: New Guinea

Subafissa kamoensis Bielawski, 1963

Distribution: New Guinea

Subafissa papuensis (Crotch, 1874)

Distribution: New Guinea

Genus ***Subcoccinella*** Agassiz et Erichson, 1845

Subcoccinella coreae Park et Yoon, 1991

Distribution: South Korea

Subcoccinella vigintiquatuorpunctata (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Palaeartic

Genus ***Toxtoma*** Weise, 1900

Toxtoma andicola Weise, 1900

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma banosi Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Ecuador

Toxtoma chaco Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Bolivia

Toxtoma chapini Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma cuzcoensis Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma disparans Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma forsteri Mader, 1958

Distribution: Bolivia

Toxtoma gentilis Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Bolivia

Toxtoma guerini Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Bolivia

Toxtoma haywardi Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Ecuador

Toxtoma hiekei Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Bolivia

Toxtoma huanucoi Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma humboldti (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Bolivia

Toxtoma imitator Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma jujuyi Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Argentina

Toxtoma leechi Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma locotalis Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Bolivia

Toxtoma longicrura Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma mimetica Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma murilloi Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Colombia

Toxtoma nunenmacheri Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma opacula (Crotch, 1874)

Distribution: Ecuador

Toxtoma opulenta (Weise, 1902)

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma orbicula Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma pilifera (Weise, 1895)

Distribution: Bolivia

Toxtoma pulchra (Weise, 1900)

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma rosae Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma rugulosa Weise, 1901

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma soukupi Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma townsendi Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma tridentata Gordon, 19975

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma venusta (Erichson, 1847)

Distribution: Peru

Toxtoma weyrauchi Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Peru

Tribe ***Cynegetini*** Thomson, 1866

Genus ***Bambusicola*** Fursch, 1975

Bambusicola aberraticus (Fursch, 1975)

Distribution: Zaire

Bambusicola bambusae (Mader, 1941)

Distribution: Zaire

Bambusicola centralis (Sicard, 1912)

Distribution: Uganda, Rwanda, Zaire

Bambusicola tonsus Fursch, 1986

Distribution: Zaire

Genus ***Cynegetis*** Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Cynegetis impunctata (Linnaeus, 1767)

Distribution: Europe (Poland, Hungary, Austria, German, Denmark, France, W. Russia), Asian Russia (Mareitimie Prov.), N. Korea

Cynegetis syriaca (Mader, 1958)

Distribution: Turkey, Iran, Syria

Genus *Damatula* Gordon, 1975

Damatula carnegiana Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Brazil

Damatula colombiana Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Colombia

Damatula disjuncta Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Brazil

Damatula earina Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Brazil

Damatula fairmairii Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Brazil

Damatula porioides (Weise, 1900)
Distribution: Colombia

Damatula schwarzi Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Panama

Damatula smarti Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Brazil

Damatula yurimagi Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Brazil

Genus *Lorma* Gordon, 1975

Lorma apicalis Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Colombia

Lorma batesii (Crotch, 1874)
Distribution: Brazil

Lorma glaucina (Mulsant, 1850)
Distribution: Brazil

Lorma haliki Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Brazil

Lorma imitator Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Colombia

Lorma nevermanni Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Costa Rica

Lorma paprzyckii Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Peru

Lorma rufoventris (Mulsant, 1850)
Distribution: Brazil

Lorma sicardi Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Bolivia

Lorma sopita Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Panama

Lorma specca Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Panama

Genus ***Mada*** Mulsant, 1850

Mada adusta Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Brazil

Mada amapa Gordon et Almeida, 1986
Distribution: Brazil

Mada amplexata (Mulsant, 1850)
Distribution: Mexico

Mada amydra Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Panama

Mada apada Gordon, 1975
Distribution: French Guiana

Mada azyoides Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Panama

Mada bechynei Gordon et Almeida, 1986
Distribution: Brazil

Mada brasilia Gordon et Almeida, 1986
Distribution: Brazil

Mada camargoi Gordon et Almeida, 1986
Distribution: Brazil

Mada cayennensis Gordon, 1975
Distribution: French Guiana, Brazil

Mada circumducta (Mulsant, 1850)
Distribution: Brazil

Mada circumflua (Mulsant, 1850)
Distribution: Brazil

Mada concentrica (Weise, 1926)
Distribution: Brazil

Mada contempta (Mulsant, 1850)
Distribution: Brazil

Mada dentata Gordon et Almeida, 1986
Distribution: Brazil

Mada desarmata (Mulsant, 1850)
Distribution: Brazil

Mada deyrollei Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Brazil

Mada dissita Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Bolivia

Mada divaricata Gordon et Almeida, 1986
Distribution: Brazil

Mada elegans Gordon 1975
Distribution: Peru

Mada flavomarginata Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Panama

Mada fraterna (Mulsant, 1850)
Distribution: French Guiana, Brazil

Mada germari Gordon et Almeida, 1986
Distribution: Brazil

Mada gounellei Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Brazil

Mada indistincta Gordon et Almeida, 1986
Distribution: Brazil

Mada inepta (Gorham, 1898)
Distribution: Costa Rica, Mexico

Mada insolitaphallus Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Peru

Mada lineatopunctata (Germar, 1924)
Distribution: Brazil

Mada mourei Gordon et Almeida, 1986
Distribution: Brazil

Mada nexophallus Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Peru

Mada pichincha Gordon et Almeida, 1986
Distribution: Ecuador

Mada polluta (Mulsant, 1850)
Distribution: Mexico

Mada pseudodamata Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Bolivia

Mada pseudofraterna Gordon, 1975
Distribution: French Guiana

Mada pseudoapada Gordon et Almeida, 1986
Distribution: Brazil

Mada rabauti Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Brazil

Mada sanguinea (Brethes, 1925)
Distribution: Brazil

Mada santaremae Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Brazil

Mada simulatrix Gordon et Almeida, 1986
Distribution: Brazil

Mada spinula Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Colombia

Mada synemia Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Ecuador

Mada virgata (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Panama, Costa Rica, Venezuela, Colombia

Mada zonula (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Brazil

Genus ***Malata*** Gordon, 1975

Malata apatela Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Guatemala

Malata burgdorfi Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Costa Rica

Malata delphinae (Gorham, 1895)

Distribution: Mexico

Malata diekei Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Mexico

Malata mitis (Mulsant, 1850)

Distribution: Mexico, Guatemala, Salvador, Costa Rica

Malata pseudomitis Gordon, 1975

Distribution: Guatemala

Genus ***Megatela*** Weise, 1906

Megatela erotyloides Weise, 1906

Distribution: Cameroon

Megatela kamerunicola (Mader, 1926)

Distribution: Cameroon

Genus ***Merma*** Weise, 1898

Merma limbata Weise, 1898

Distribution: Cameroon, Congo, Ivory Coast

Merma mediata Kapur, 1948

Distribution: Uganda

Merma rufa Fursch, 1986

Distribution: Ivory Coast

Merma spilota Weise, 1898
Distribution: Cameroon

Genus *Pseudodira* Gordon, 1975

Pseudodira clypealis Gordon, 1975
Distribution: Brazil

Genus *Tropha* Weise, 1900

Tropha obscura (Korschefsky, 1929)
Distribution: Tanzania

Tropha variabilis Weise, 1900
Distribution: Zaire, Tanzania, Mozambique

Tribe *Epivertini* Pang et Mao, 1979

Genus *Epiverta* Dieke, 1947

Epiverta chelonia (Mader, 1933)
Distribution: China

Tribe *Eremochilini* Gordon et Vandenberg, 1987

Genus *Eremochilus* Weise, 1912

Eremochilus ferrugineus (Gorham, 1899)
Distribution: Mexico

Eremochilus peregrinus Weise, 1912
Distribution: Bolivia

Eremochilus weisei Gordon et Vandenberg, 1987
Distribution: Brazil

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